

Recovery Strategy of Selected Filipino Restaurants in Tagaytay City

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Abstract: There have been a lot of people visiting Tagaytay City as one of the best tourist spots in Cavite. Due to the natural disaster – The Taal Volcano eruption, many establishments have been greatly affected especially Filipino Restaurants with alfresco dining and those near the Taal volcano. Because of the disaster, the researchers aimed to determine and analysed the gathered data concerning the significant difference of recovery strategy of selected Filipino restaurants with alfresco dining in Tagaytay City. The study's main concept is a recovery strategy. This concept has 5 factors examined by the researchers including Human Resources, Natural Resources, Capital Resources, Technology, Social and Political. Descriptive methods and online survey questionnaires via google forms were used to collect data and information. The respondents were the selected restaurant's Managers and staff. The results show that the restaurants recovered by focusing on Human resource, Technology, Social and Political factors. The respondents perceived that giving proper training and seminars greatly benefited the recovery of the establishment. The results also show that the selected restaurants have no significant difference between demographic profile, and factors such as Human resources, Natural resources, Capital resources, technology, and Social and Political.

Keywords: Natural Disaster, Quantitative Research, Recovery Strategy, Tagaytay City.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism and the hospitality industry are one of the most known industries worldwide. Whether it's in beaches, mountains or cities, tourism and hospitality are always present. It is said that these industries are one of the most exposed to different kinds of disasters due to their own location and hazard prone regions. According to Walters (2015) the image a tourist holds of a destination is recognized as being of high importance, this is due to the influence it has on the destinations a tourist chooses to visit. There are many different factors which affect how a potential visitor will see a destination; these may include information found in advertising and that obtained by word of mouth. When it comes to disasters specifically, a large factor influencing the image of a destination in a tourist's mind is the global distribution of information via the media. This can lead to a negative impression of locations affected by natural disasters.

According to the World Bank (2020), the Philippines is one of the most natural hazard prone countries in the world. It is due to the country's location along the ring of fire or typhoon belt - a region in the Pacific Ocean where earthquakes and volcanic eruptions occur.

One of the most recent natural disasters that the Philippines faced was the Taal volcano eruption. Taal is one of the most active volcanoes in the Philippines with a total of 33 known historical eruptions, Perla J Delos Reyes et al (2018). And last January 12, 2020, its 34th known volcanic eruption occurred that affected a lot of cities, especially Batangas and Tagaytay. As stated in Pinnacle.ph (2020) DOT tagged Tagaytay as the best tourist destination in CALABARZON. Tagaytay is a second-class city in the province of Cavite and has a booming industry. Because of its cool weather especially during November up to middle of March, eco-friendly environment, hotel establishments, amusement parks

and restaurants with different delicious delicacies, it is one of the best vacation places to visit. Tagaytay is continuously evolving to a successful tourist attraction but due to natural disasters such as the Taal volcano eruption, the economy on Tagaytay declined.

Reported by GMA News Online (2020) several business establishments in Tagaytay City were affected following the Taal volcano's phreatic eruption. There was a huge drop in the amounts of tourists and visitors in the city, which caused hotels, restaurants and amusement parks to close temporarily.

Pinnacle.ph (2020) stated that if effects are widespread, the economy may take a hit in terms of inflation, higher cost of goods due to imbalance of supply and demand and logistical challenges and possible decrease in economic activity. Business operations may temporarily be suspended for extended periods of time or may even shut down.

According to Food Safety Act of 2013, also known as Republic Act No. 10611, was passed in order to "strengthen the country's food safety regulatory framework to protect consumer health and enable trade.", these laws offer the protection of consumers from business malpractices and from substandard or hazardous products, among other things of local foods and food products, and for other purposes.

As stated in FSIS/FDA Guidelines for retail and food service establishments affected by natural or other disasters, the guidelines provide emergency action food safety suggestions and information for retail and foodservice establishments resuming business in the aftermath of natural or other kinds of disasters.

With all the information collected, the researchers would like to understand the risk management standards of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City. The researchers would want to get the most effective design to reduce disaster risk and to determine how restaurant establishments in Tagaytay start or do their marketing to attract guests. The result and findings of this study will be beneficial to the future hospitality industry in Tagaytay. Through understanding the experience and perspective of students, restaurant managers and staff would be able to recommend a better recovery strategy.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. #1 Input Process Output

Figure #1 The Input-Process-Output will be used for the direct connection between relevant factors that may affect and impact the customers' predilection to dine in the restaurants in Tagaytay. The figures above show the Input variables which are contributing factors that may affect the decision of the customers. The Input above includes the demographic profile and talks about the participant's age, gender, and years of service in the establishment. It also shows the different strategies that have been used by different restaurants in Tagaytay City. Reliability talks about the dependability of the structure and the quality of the products. It is important to know and fix the damage done by the disaster. Assurance is also important especially to the staff to have special training so that they will not panic in case of unpredictable disaster and assure the safety of the customers. And lastly, the advertisement talks about how the company promotes their

establishment and attracts more customers by ensuring their safety and satisfaction. The Process includes data gathering by using an online survey questionnaire as the research instrument. The data that will be gathered will be analyzed by the researchers by using statistical tools. Lastly, the Output of the study will determine and propose the foremost or the most effective restaurant strategy that is used by the selected restaurant in Tagaytay. Another output will be the suggestion/recommendation on how to further improve the strategist that has been used by the restaurant in Tagaytay.

Statement of the Problem

The researchers know that along with this study, Data will be gathered, facts will be recognized, and problems will be solved. Restaurants have been affected by the recent Taal Volcano Eruption. These are the questions that are aimed to be answered either during the study or after every detail has been served.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Nationality
 - 1.4 Years of employment
 - 1.5 Job Position
2. How do the respondents assessed the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of:
 - 2.1 Human Resources
 - 2.2 Natural Resources
 - 2.3 Capital Resources
 - 2.4 Technology
 - 2.5 Social
3. Is there any significant difference in recovery strategy of selected Filipino restaurants in terms of:
 - 3.1 Human Resources
 - 3.2 Natural Resources
 - 3.3 Capital Resources
 - 3.4 Technology
 - 3.5 Social
4. What Restaurant's Recovery Strategy can be Recommended and can be improved in selected restaurants affected by the disaster.

Statement of Hypothesis

There is no significant difference among the recovery strategies of selected Filipino restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Human resource, Natural Resource, Capital Resource, Technology, and Social.

Related Literature

According to Masotti (2017), the Italians used the expression "al fresco" to mean "in the chill" or "in the cool." Meaning the al fresco dining is located at a cool place that is intended to make people chill and relax. It is an outdoor dining restaurant that has a nice scenic view.

Based on Rouhanizadeh, Kermanshachi & Nipa (2020), Destructive natural disasters affect countries around the whole world. To recover from a natural disaster, a manager needs to make various decisions; however, what makes the post disaster decision making unique is lack of time to make the optimum decision.

As mentioned by Olshansky (2017) Great natural disasters are rare, but their aftermath can change the fortunes of a city or region forever.

Based on Brush and Crocetti, Disaster Recovery Plan is a documented approach that describes how organizations can quickly resume work after unplanned incidents. It aims to help organizations resolve data losses and recovery systems functionally so that it can perform in the aftermath of an incident, even if it's at a minimal level. It also stated that Recovery strategies define an organization's plan for responding to an incident and recovery plans are derived from recovery strategies. In determining recovery strategy, organizations should consider budgets, insurance coverage, resources, technology, data, etc.

As Stated by Cuevas et al (2020), Environmental issues are a concern for most countries. Sustaining the environment is a vital practice for the food industry because they produce more waste, use large amounts of energy and natural resources. It also stated that customers always demand for a safe environment, quality products, and good service. Implementing Green Practices in the company helps to protect the environment and the excellent prestige of the business.

According to Theodora (2020) Spatial planning is becoming a particularly interesting aspect of disaster prevention and management, especially in a context where nongovernmental stakeholders of various forms, replay an important part in making decisions and are creating a new social actor network as a result.

Based on Camillo, Angelo (2020) the majority of foodservice operations are significantly reliant on technology. Even a brief halt in corporate operations might result in significant financial losses. Restaurants that rely significantly on reservation systems, such as "OpenTable" (2020), for example, may suffer a significant loss if the system is hacked or infected with a nasty virus, resulting in significant downtime.

As reported by the Institute for Sustainable Development 2018. On the island of Hawaii, the Recovery Plan is meant to serve as an organized, actionable roadmap for business recovery, company expansion, job creation, and private and public investment. It also contains funding measures to help the economy recover and improve what was lost due to the 2018 disasters.

Stated by Prateek Agarwal (2021), economic growth is one of the most important indicators of a healthy economy and it has 6 factors: Human Capital, natural resources, Capital resources, technology, law and population.

Based on the article shared by Nitisha, economic growth can be defined as a positive change in the level of goods and services produced over a certain period, 5 factors affect the growth of the economy of a country, human resources, natural resources, capital resources, technology, social and political.

One of the most important responsibilities of human resources is to prepare for a disaster including safety initiatives, communication with employees and headlining management efforts. Organizations have a duty to protect their worker's safety while in duty. Greg Byrne (2017)

According to UNEP (2009), one of the prioritized issues of the International Recovery Platform is how to assess and respond to the impacts of a disaster. Some of the environmental issues typically encountered in a recovery setting are the release of hazardous substances and debris into the environment, water salination and contamination, sanitation, including the management of solid waste, reestablishing livelihoods, and the effect of relief and recovery efforts on the environment. To assist decision makers, good practices on: how to assess environmental impacts post-disasters effectively; what constitutes environmentally sound relief and recovery operations; how to engage environmental actors early in disaster recovery; and what environmental related support and guidance is available; are needed.

Stated by Troy Segal (2020), physical Capital or simply "Capital" consists of tangible, human-made goods that assist in the process of creating a product or service.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter clearly explains the methods that will be used in this study. It provides information on who will be the participants and how they will be sampled.

A. *Research Design*

This is a Quantitative Research that will use a Descriptive Research design that will be used to determine the Recovery Strategy of Selected Filipino Restaurants in Tagaytay City.

As stated by (Bhandari,2020) Quantitative Research is the process of collecting and analysing numerical data. Patterns and averages can be found, forecasts can be made, causality can be tested, and results can be extrapolated to larger groups. A population, circumstance, or phenomena is described in descriptive research, a subtype of study. Instead of addressing the why of a research topic, it concentrates on addressing the how, what, when, and where questions. (FormplusBlog,2020) In this study, online survey forms will be used via Google Forms that will be used in gathering the data. As stated by Pollfish,2015 Online surveys are a great market research tool in order to explore if there is a market for a new product or service or for validating a new business idea.

B. Research Locale

The research main setting is within the vicinity of Tagaytay City. This is because the respondents will be the different Managers and Staffs of the Selected Filipino Restaurants in Tagaytay City. One of the reasons why the researchers chose this research setting is because there is a big number of food services in Tagaytay City which are greatly affected by the recent Taal Volcano eruption. Secondly, Tagaytay City is one of the most famous tourist spots in CALABARZON. And lastly, the researchers would like to share the results and findings of the study to these restaurants that are greatly affected by the said natural disaster to improve their recovery strategy.

C. Participants of the Study

The respondents were limited to Managers and Staff of the TOP 7 Selected Filipino restaurants in Tagaytay City based on Trip Advisor with the category Al-Fresco, Filipino-Asian Cuisines and Mid-range Prices. The researcher selected these specific respondents because they are the one who operates the restaurant daily and for sure they have a deeper knowledge and understanding when it comes to their recovery strategy after the Natural Disaster strikes their restaurant.

The researchers will be using a Cluster Sampling. It is a sampling technique where the clusters are selected randomly and, in each cluster, they all have an equal chance to be selected. For the sample size, the researcher will consider Neuman's (2006) wherein the recommended sample size should be 30% if the total population of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City is under 1000 managers and staff.

D. Research Instrument and Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers will be using the primary and secondary sources of data. To collect the primary data, the proponents will be using online survey questionnaires. The questionnaires that will be provided are in a 4-point Likert Scale. According to Whitney (2015) A Likert Scale is a type of rating scale used to measure attitudes or opinions of the respondents. Once the questionnaires are approved, they will be given a link connected to google forms through their social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and lastly their official websites and they will be given ample time to finish the survey before being collected. According to Pollfish (2015) Online surveys are a great market research tool in order to explore if there is a market for a new product or service or for validating a new business idea. Since in this time of pandemic we can't have a regular survey wherein they will be handed paper and face-to-face survey.

E. Data Treatment and Analysis

With all the data that has been gathered, the researchers will properly be tallied, analyzed, and treated the data with the help of their statistician to be able to use the appropriate statistician tool/s. Lastly, the results and findings will be documented, interpreted and presented after all the data analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results of the data analysis.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of Managers and Staffs of the Different Al-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Age

	Frequency	Percent
Age		
≤20	2	5.1
21 to 30	27	69.2
31 to 40	10	25.6

Table 1.1 shows the age of respondents in which 69.2% are ages 21-30 with a total of 27 for the frequency and 25.6% are ages 31-40 with a total of 10 frequency out of 39 and 5.1% are ages 20 and below with frequency of 2.

The result shows that the majority of the respondents are 20-30 years old. This shows that the restaurants in Tagaytay chose to hire younger people to maximize profit. Based on an article written by Jose Alba, when unexpected events happen, younger people are better at coping and adapting to sudden change. This can benefit in the shifting landscape of the modern-day workday where processes, technologies and priorities are changing. Young individuals have an advantage in today's workplace since it is more agile, flexible, and fast-paced than ever before.

Based on the gathered data of the researchers, the age 21-30 have the highest percentage wherein at this age are most likely to work in the restaurant and most of them are managers and staff of the different restaurants in Tagaytay. The least amount of percentage is the age 20 and below wherein at this age, people are just about to finish college because of the K-12 implementation they have an additional year compared to the old curriculum.

With this result, it can be seen clearly that more establishments prefer younger people because they can easily adapt in their work environment

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of Managers and Staffs of the Different Al-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Gender

Gender		
Male	20	51.3
Female	19	48.7

Table 1.2 shows the percentage and frequency in terms of Gender. The data shows that 51.3% with a frequency of 20 are Male and 48.7% and frequency of 19 out of 39 are Female.

The result shows that there are more male respondents than female. This shows that men are more obligated to work for financial duties. According to Epieta (2019), labor force participation of women in the Philippines is 30% lower than men. The gender roles still appear to greatly influence the decision to employment, men assume the role of providing for the family financially, and women assume the role of domestic duties. This shows why there are more male employees than females in this study.

Based on the data gathered from the researchers, there are more males working in a restaurant with a higher percentage of 51.3% than the female with 48.7%.

Therefore, with this result it can be clearly seen that establishments prefer male because the work focuses more on doing and carrying heavy items that's why they need more of male staff.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of Managers and Staffs of the Different Al-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Nationality

Nationality		
Filipino	39	100.0

Table 1.3 shows the percentage and frequency of Managers and Staffs in Different Al-fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City based on their Nationality were All Filipinos with a total of 100%.

The result shows that Filipino restaurants chose Filipino citizens to be their employees for it is easier to preserve, present and continue the culture with the same ethnicity. Based on a blog in jobpinoy.com, work and office culture are different in every country. Thus, the Philippine work environment has this common business custom that goes all the way from different Filipino values. Being hospitable, friendly, family-oriented, generous, and hardworking, are the common customs of the Filipinos. It also stated that working with Filipinos is an exalting experience to everybody.

Based on the Data, 100% of the Managers and Staff are Filipinos basically because the restaurant itself is Filipino. There is no other nationality better than Filipinos in serving their own culture.

Therefore, with this result, it can greatly affect and attract people more to their restaurant since it is Filipino Cuisine therefore it should only have Filipino staff.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of Managers and Staffs of the Different AI-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of years of employment

Years of employment		
5 years and below	32	82.1
6 years and above	7	17.9

Table 1. 4 Demographic Profile in terms of Managers and Staff years of employment in Different AI-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City. The data shows that 82.1% with a frequency of 32 are five years and below employed and 17.9% with a frequency of 7 are 6 years and above employed.

The result shows that most of the respondents have 5 years and below experience in the industry. This reflects the age of the employees. Companies tend to hire younger employees, so employment is also short. According to Ferguson, Long-term employees are loyal to the company, but you must work to keep them as such. Having good benefits for the employees can keep them and motivate them in achieving their quota but also giving them rewards wherein they will enjoy working for your establishment/company. Employees prefer companies that help them gain knowledge on a day-to-day basis.

Based on the data gathered from the researchers, there are more employees employed five years and below than six years and above.

Therefore, this result will affect the experience and knowledge of the staff based on their different experience, as we all know the more, they last to that establishment the more knowledge and experience they can gain.

Table 1.5 Demographic Profile of Managers and Staffs of the Different AI-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of job position

		Freque ncy	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulati ve Percent
Valid	Cashier	3	7.7	7.7	7.7
	Crew	17	43.6	43.6	51.3
	Manager	6	15.4	15.4	66.7
	Receptio nist	1	2.6	2.6	69.2
	Staff	12	30.8	30.8	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.5 Demographic Profile in terms of their Job Position in Different AI-Fresco Restaurants in Tagaytay City. The data shows that 43.6% with a frequency of 17 are Crew members, 30.8% with a frequency of 12 are Staff, 15.4% with a frequency are Managers, 7.7 % with a frequency of 3 are Cashier, and 2.6% with a frequency is a receptionist.

According to Adkins (2019), Service Crew members are workers in the food industry who are responsible for preparing and serving food to the customers. As we all know, many people such as students, prefer working as a service crew to help them sustain their allowance needed for schooling because they can be a part-timer in working as a service crew.

Based on the data gathered from the researchers, there are more crew working in a restaurant with a higher percentage of 43.6% than a receptionist with the lowest percentage of 2.6%.

2. How do the respondents assessed the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of:

Table 2.1 The respondents assessed the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Human Resources

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The employees are trained properly especially in certain circumstances such as natural disasters.	3.69	0.52	Strongly agree
2. The employees are required to attend seminars about pre/post disaster recovery before working to the establishment	3.62	0.59	Strongly agree
3. The company gives benefits to the employees such as health insurance in case of an emergency.	3.67	0.53	Strongly agree
4. The employees have protective gears in case of a sudden volcanic eruption.	3.64	0.54	Strongly agree
5. The company offers a shuttle for their employees' safety.	3.41	0.88	Strongly agree
6. The company provides protective gears to the employees.	3.64	0.54	Strongly agree
7. The company has a complete emergency kit for their employees.	3.62	0.54	Strongly agree
8. The employees were not paid due to financial problems of the business.	2.36	0.67	Disagree
9. Employees were asked to help in renovating the restaurants.	2.33	0.62	Disagree
10. The labor fee was lowered due to damage costs	2.36	0.58	Disagree
Overall Mean	3.32	0.75	Strongly Agree (Very High Level of Recovery)

In terms of Human Resource, resulting overall mean of 3.32 implies strong agreement or implying a very high level of recovery in terms of human resources. Specifically, the highest mean of 3.69 implies that they strongly agree that they are trained properly especially in certain circumstances such as natural disaster. Followed by 2nd highest mean of 3.67 also denoting that they strongly agree that their company gives benefits to them such as health insurance in case of an emergency. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 2.33, which implies that they disagree that they were asked to help in renovating the restaurants, while mean of 2.36 also implies that they disagree that they are not paid due to financial problems of the business, as well as disagreeing that the labor fee was lowered due to damage cost.

The selected restaurants in Tagaytay City have a very high level of recovery in terms of human resource by taking care of their staff, giving proper training, seminars, and benefits. Training employees lessens the losses by knowing what to do in certain circumstances. According to Majid Ahmed Al Qasimi (2021), training is a managerial, technological, realistic, and scientific approach that maximizes work efficiency, and improves the use of the available human capital of the company. For the lowest rank, the respondents disagree that they were asked to help in renovating the restaurant. Asking to work outside their duties and responsibilities will lessen the enthusiasm of the employees.

The table shows that the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City got "Strongly Agree" interpretation for giving training, seminars, benefits, proper gears, and emergency kits. And "Disagree" interpretation for lowered labor fee, additional work, and not being paid during the disaster. With this, the proponents perceived a very high level of recovery strategy in terms of human resource.

Table 2.2 The respondents assessed the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Natural Resources.

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.The company have a back-up generator for emergency black out.	3.08	0.48	Agree
2. The restaurant finds a new water supplier to serve a cleaner supply than the old one.	2.67	0.74	Agree
3. There are delays with the supplies, so the restaurant decided to switch to another supplier.	2.74	0.72	Agree
4. The Alfresco area is renovated so customers can view the Taal's changes.	2.54	0.76	Agree
5. The restaurant has its own vegetable garden after the disaster.	2.36	0.78	Disagree
6. The alfresco or the outdoor seats were not usable because of dust and ashes.	3.44	0.64	Strongly Agree
7. The electrical power of the restaurant was cut off.	3.41	0.55	Strongly Agree
8. The quantity of the foods that can be served was limited due to lack of supplies.	2.82	0.64	Agree
Overall Mean	2.28	0.82	Disagree (Low)

In terms of Natural Resource, resulting in an overall mean of 2.28 implying low levels of recovery in terms of natural resources. Specifically, the highest mean is 3.44 implying that they strongly agree that alfresco or outdoor seats were not usable because of dust and ashes. This is followed by a mean of 3.41 which denotes strong agreement that the electrical power of the restaurant was cut-off. On the other hand, the least mean 2.36 implies that they disagree that the restaurant has its own vegetable garden after the disaster. This is followed by a mean of 2.54 which denotes that they agree that the Alfresco area is renovated so customers can view the Taal's changes.

The selected restaurants in Tagaytay City have a low level of recovery in terms of natural resources for their alfresco or the outdoor seats were not usable because of dusts and ashes, electrical power was cut off, and not having a vegetable garden after the disaster. As an alfresco restaurant, the place where customers stay to eat is not usable is a big factor that affects the recovery of the business. Followed by having the electrical power cut off where it is the main need in restaurants for keeping refrigerated goods fresh. As stated in Cashmanequipment.com, for the service industry, having no light or power means a dead business. No electricity means any refrigerated products will go bad. As for the lowest rank which the company does not have, their green garden can be improved. This will help the restaurants to increase their profits. According to ipl.org, there is a growing trend and interest in sustainability of the environment in the hospitality industry. A lot of operators of food establishments have participated in efforts to help save resources as well as utility costs not only for the benefits of their business but also for the benefit of the environment. Green practices are defined as sustainable environmental management methods in which the operators convert natural resources into better outputs for better financial costs.

The table shows that the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City got "Strongly Agree" interpretation for the alfresco area is not usable and electrical power was cut off. "Agree" interpretation for having a back-up generator, new water suppliers, renovated alfresco area, and limited foods can be served due to lack of supplies. And finally, "Disagree" interpretation for not having their own vegetable garden that may improve the restaurant's financial costs with this, the proponents perceived a low level of recovery strategy in terms of Natural Resources.

Table 2.3. The respondents perceived the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Capital resources.

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The restaurant improved the menu that is in trend to attract more customers.	2.90	0.72	Agree
2. The establishment is insured if natural disasters happen such as fire, earthquake, volcano eruption, etc.	3.23	0.71	Agree
3. The restaurant went under renovation after the disaster.	2.74	0.72	Agree
4. The interior and the alfresco space of the restaurant is improved.	2.87	0.73	Agree
5. The Restaurant increased the prices of the menu.	2.44	0.64	Disagree
6. The restaurant's wall was cracked due to earthquakes caused by the Taal eruption.	3.44	0.55	Strongly agree
7. The Roof collapsed due to heavy ashes from the Volcano.	2.85	0.71	Agree
8. The furniture and tableware inside the restaurant are damaged heavily.	3.00	0.56	Agree
Overall Mean	2.49	0.84	Disagree (Low level)

In terms of Capital Resource, Results of an overall mean of 2.49 suggest that the level of recovery in terms of capital resources is still low. Specifically, the highest mean is 3.44 implying that they strongly agree that the restaurant's wall was cracked due to earthquakes of the Taal eruption. This is followed by a mean of 3.23, which implies that they agree that the establishment is insured if natural disasters happen such as fire, earthquake, volcano eruption. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 2.44 which means that they disagree that the restaurant increased the prices of the menu.

The selected restaurants in Tagaytay City have a low level of recovery in terms of Capital resource for having the walls cracked which is the main structure of the business. In addition, the roofs collapsed due to heavy ashes, and damaged

furniture. These factors are negative and affect the overall mean. The positive sides indicated that the establishment is insured if natural disasters happen, they improved the menu, the restaurant went under renovation, and did not increase the prices of the menu. According to Insureon.com, disaster recovery plans are a very essential document for all small businesses. It helps the operators or business owners to respond effectively to catastrophic events. Based on their survey, 61% of the respondents do not have a business continuity plan in place. Disaster recovery plans help minimize the damage to business properties. Once the property is damaged, insurance can potentially cover the damage. This also makes sure that your company will not put you out of business in case of disaster. For the lowest rank, which is not increasing the prices of the menu, there is no problem in it, but the restaurants can improve the prices to maximize the profit and make more money.

The table shows that the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City got “Strongly Agree” interpretation to walls being cracked due to earthquake. “Agree” interpretations to improved menu, insured establishment, restaurant went under renovation, interior and alfresco space were improved, roof collapsed, and furniture and tableware were damaged heavily. Lastly, a “Disagree” interpretation for increasing the prices in the menu which means that their product is not affected by the disaster very much. With this, the proponents perceived a low level of recovery strategy in terms of capital resources.

Table 2.4 The respondents perceived the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Technology resources.

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The Restaurant added some additional delivery services.	3.00	0.83	Agree
2. We used social media/websites to advertise more about the restaurant.	3.56	0.55	Strongly agree
3. We promote our website through Facebook sponsored posts.	3.49	0.60	Strongly agree
4. We bought a new aircon to replace the old ones.	2.74	0.75	Agree
5. The bulbs and other lightings are replaced with new lights	2.82	0.76	Agree
4. The vehicles for delivery and transportation are not operational.	3.44	0.55	Strongly agree
6. The appliances such as aircon, vacuum, fan, etc. are not operational or damaged due to disaster.	2.77	0.71	Agree
Overall Mean	2.77	0.94	Agree (High Level of recovery)

In terms of Technology, the resulting overall mean of 2.77 implies an agreement or implying high level of recovery in terms of technology, where the highest mean of 3.56 implies strong agreement that they used social media / websites to advertise more about the restaurant. This is followed by a mean of 3.49 also implying that they strongly agree that they promote their website through Facebook sponsored posts. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 2.74 which means that they agree that they bought new aircon to replace the old ones, while followed by mean of 2.77 which still implies that they agree that the appliances are not operational or damaged due to disaster.

The selected restaurants in Tagaytay City have a very high level of recovery in terms of technology resource for using social media/websites, promoting through Facebook sponsored posts, added additional delivery services, and new bulbs are replaced with new lights. According to Giraldo (2010), technology has played an important role in the rise of the service sector in developed countries, contributing to improved productivity. There is a new role for technology in services, which is the source for innovations. Since technology is enabling and facilitating innovation in service firms. It contributes to respond properly to the challenges of modern economy, gain sustainable competitive advantage for the business, improve performances in service innovation and generate more variety in response to the customer’s needs.

The table shows that the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City got a “Strongly Agree” interpretation on using media for promoting business, and not operational delivery transportation. “Agree” interpretation on additional delivery services, replacing old air conditioners with new ones, new bulbs, and not operational damaged appliances due to disaster. With this, the proponents perceive that there is a high level of recovery strategy in the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City.

Table 2.5 The respondents perceived the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of Social and Political resources.

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The restaurant advertises the business through social media by giving promotions.	3.79	0.52	Strongly agree
2. The restaurant did not have any problems following Republic Act No. 10611.	3.77	0.43	Strongly agree
3. The employees are asked to the social media platform page of the restaurant to widen the range of customers.	3.44	0.75	Strongly agree
4. The restaurant preserves the culture and tradition they had before the eruption to attract their old customers to come again.	3.74	0.44	Strongly agree
5. There are no customers coming to the restaurants because of ashes and dust.	3.36	0.63	Strongly agree
Overall Mean	3.28	0.63	Strongly agree (Very High)

In terms of Social and Political, resulting overall mean of 3.28 implies strong agreement or implying a very high level of recovery in terms of social, where the highest mean of 3.79 implies strong agreement that their restaurant advertises the business through social media by giving promotions. This is followed by a mean of 3.77 also suggesting that they strongly agree that their restaurant did not have any problems following Republic Act No. 10611. The lowest mean is 3.36, which still implies that they strongly agree that there are no customers coming to the restaurants because of ashes and dust.

The selected restaurants in Tagaytay City have a high level of recovery in terms of Social and Political factors by having their establishment following the laws and regulations, utilizing the staff to promote the company, and keeping the tradition and culture of the restaurants. These will help the restaurant's reputation to increase. Customers will love delicious and safe foods especially those who are craving Filipino Cuisines and culture. According to the article shared by Nitisha, the social and political factors greatly affect the growth of the economy. This includes the culture, traditions, values, obeying laws, and policies. According to Kim (2015), social media provide low-cost advertising to increase market share and boost restaurant sales.

This table shows that the participants of the study in Tagaytay City got "Strongly Agree" interpretation for advertising the business through social media by giving promotions, the restaurants did not have any problems following Republic Act No. 10611, the employees were asked to share the social media platform page of the restaurant to widen the range of customers, restaurant preserves the culture and tradition they had before the eruption to attract their old customers to come again, and lastly, there are no customer coming to the restaurant because of ashes and dusts. With this, the proponents perceived that there is a very high level of recovery in terms of Social and political.

3. Are there significant differences in recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City in terms of:

3.1 Human Resource

Restaurants	Mean	SD	F	p value	Decision	Conclusion
Restaurant A	3.33	0.43	1.454	0.22	Accept Null	Not significant
Restaurant B	2.80	0.34				
Restaurant C	3.28	0.53				
Restaurant D	3.26	0.49				
Restaurant E	3.70	0.00				
Restaurant F	3.45	0.43				
Restaurant G	3.50	0.45				
Restaurant H	3.23	0.55				

Table 3.1 shows that the resulting p value of 0.22 which exceeds the level of significance of 0.05 denotes that the mean recovery strategy in terms of human resources is not significantly different among different restaurants. Although not significant, it can still be described that Restaurant E has the highest mean score of 3.70, while lowest is from Restaurant B of 2.80.

Valerie Bolden-Barrett claims that checklists of items to think about are used to create HR business continuity plans. The two most pressing issues are protecting lives and providing serious injury treatment for workers. Evacuation procedures should include transportation for disabled employees and take into account customers and vendors visiting the work site. HR must take into consideration how staff should be trained to handle crises, informed of emergencies, transported to safety, and cross-trained for jobs identified as "essential." An excellent HR plan considers how staff may be impacted by payroll delays, office closures, schedule adjustments, and layoffs and how to reduce potential problems. A plan may include setting up food and money for emergencies as well as designating shelters for evacuees.

3.2 Natural Resources

Restaurants	Mean	SD	F	p value	Decision	Conclusion
Restaurant A	2.07	0.16	1.716	0.142	Accept Null	Not significant
Restaurant B	2.66	0.31				
Restaurant C	2.35	0.37				
Restaurant D	2.34	0.35				
Restaurant E	2.19	0.22				
Restaurant F	2.17	0.30				
Restaurant G	2.15	0.27				
Restaurant H	2.34	0.16				

Table 3.2 shows that the resulting p value of 0.142 which exceeds the level of significance of 0.05 denotes that the mean recovery strategy in terms of natural resources is not significantly different among different restaurants. Although not significant, it can still be described that Restaurant B has the highest mean score of 2.66, while lowest is from Restaurant A with only 2.07 mean score. It reveals that, on average, all of the restaurants have responded effectively, and that human resource is a good component for a faster recovery.

The alarming rates of food loss and waste (FLW) in the food supply chain (FSC), as well as how they contribute to the depletion of natural resources and the growth in greenhouse gas emissions, have been brought to the public's notice, according to Shahla M. Wunderlich Globally. The last ten years have seen an increase in the sense of urgency among academics, world leaders, government, and non-government organizations to conduct research and develop thorough plans and goals to address and lower the rates of global FLW. This is due to the discovery of the cascading effects of this interrelationship. FLW not only reduces the amount of food that is accessible but also the availability of the numerous natural resources needed to create food..

3.3 Capital Resource

Restaurants	Mean	SD	F	p value	Decision	Conclusion
Restaurant A	2.78	0.06	2.638	0.029	Reject Null	At least one is significant
Restaurant B	2.81	0.24				
Restaurant C	2.48	0.21				
Restaurant D	2.50	0.22				
Restaurant E	2.31	0.22				
Restaurant F	2.35	0.22				
Restaurant G	2.43	0.31				
Restaurant H	2.31	0.41				

Table 3.3 that the resulting p value of 0.029 which is less than level of significance of 0.05 suggest that at least one restaurant has significantly different mean capital resources recovery scores. Specifically, pairwise comparison reveals that Restaurant A (2.78) and Restaurant B (2.81) have significantly higher recoveries on capital resources as compared to Restaurant E (2.31), Restaurant F (2.35) and Restaurant H (2.31). It reveals that Restaurants A and B have a stronger capital resource strategy, which can enable Restaurants C, E, F, G, H recover more quickly.

Michael S. Kaufman, Lena G. Goldberg, and Jill Avery assert that it has never been simple to succeed financially in the restaurant business. The average restaurant's annual sales hovers around \$1 million and produces an operational profit of barely 4-5 percent in this highly fragmented industry, which is dominated by independent owners and operators to a 70

percent ratio. For tiny independent businesses, a financially viable business plan is frequently challenging. Therefore, things become more bad when a crisis the size of the COVID-19 and other catastrophes forces restaurants to close, and their revenue sinks to nil overnight. In contrast to the oligopolistic aviation industry, where a few huge enterprises can readily band together to push for government support, government initiatives intended to help small businesses typically ignore the concerns of restaurant owners and the unique realities and difficulties facing their industry.

3.4 Technology

Restaurants	Mean	SD	F	p value	Decision	Conclusion
Restaurant A	2.75	0.18	1.224	0.32	Accept Null	Not significant
Restaurant B	2.68	0.14				
Restaurant C	2.94	0.30				
Restaurant D	2.88	0.31				
Restaurant E	2.54	0.24				
Restaurant F	2.81	0.22				
Restaurant G	2.74	0.12				
Restaurant H	2.71	0.31				

Table 3.4 shows that Resulting p value of 0.32 which exceeds the level of significance of 0.05 denotes that the mean recovery strategy in terms of technology resources is not significantly different among different restaurants. Although not significant, it can still be described that Restaurant C has the highest mean score of 2.94, while lowest is Restaurant E with only 2.54 mean score. It demonstrates that technology plays a significant role in assisting a restaurant's recovery.

As written by Jordan Ghaffari Online ordering has stormed through the F&B industry due to state guidelines limiting capacity. Many businesses include contactless pick-up or delivery to ensure customers can safely order from their favorite restaurants. Based on Square's 2021 Future of Restaurants report, 75% of restaurants plan to offer contactless ordering and payment options across all channels (Square). To help with high delivery demand, third-party services like Uber Eats and DoorDash rose in popularity. Although there are commissions associated with these third-party services– which can vary from 10-25%– they can enhance revenue by providing exceptional convenience to customers.

3.5 Social

Restaurants	Mean	SD	F	p value	Decision	Conclusion
Restaurant A	3.15	0.55	0.883	0.531	Accept Null	Not significant
Restaurant B	3.05	0.19				
Restaurant C	3.28	0.30				
Restaurant D	3.20	0.38				
Restaurant E	3.45	0.10				
Restaurant F	3.33	0.16				
Restaurant G	3.32	0.30				
Restaurant H	3.45	0.19				

Table 3.5 shows that Resulting p value of 0.531 which exceeds the level of significance of 0.05 denotes that the mean recovery strategy in terms of social resources is not significantly different among different restaurants. Although not significant, it can still be described that Restaurant E and Restaurant H have the highest mean score of 3.45, while lowest is from Restaurant B with only 3.05 mean score. It demonstrates that social can be improved and has a significant impact on how quickly a restaurant can recover.

According to Danielle Calamaras, state governments have established organizations to assist local governments, charitable organizations, and private companies get through emergency situations, whether they are brought on by Mother Nature or human error. This is done to help business prepare for the humanitarian crises that invariably accompany major disasters. These organizations work to safeguard local communities, regional economies, and local natural habitats, but they can only do so much to help prepare businesses for catastrophic situations. Because of this, organizations frequently hire firms that are experts in handling major catastrophes to provide services. People may encounter a variety of different emergency circumstances or disasters.

4. What Restaurant's Recovery Strategy can be recommended and can be improved in selected restaurants affected by the disaster.

The Recovery Strategy output was based on the lowest ranking of each factor such as the Human Resource, Natural Resource, Capital Resource, Technology and Social. Wherein the researchers recommended 5 recovery strategies that can be used to improve their establishment after being affected by a disaster.

Recovery Strategy of Selected Filipino Restaurants in Tagaytay City

- 01**

Maximize Human Resources

To ensure that you maximize the human capital by hiring and giving them extra work to lessen the cost of hiring others to clean and renovate the establishment

- 02**

Green Practices/ Vegetable Garden

Having Vegetable Garden benefits the financial costs, it can save delivery expenses and cost of raw ingredients.

- 03**

Increase Menu Prices

Increasing the Menu Prices will help the restaurants lessen the losses while recovering from the damage taken

- 04**

Maintenance of Appliances

By having a regular Maintenance will help prevent the thick ashes to damage the appliances

- 05**

Prioritize the Cleanliness and Safety of the Customers

Prioritizing the Cleanliness of the Establishment amidst the Natural Disasters so that Customers would not hesitate to come and dine at the Restaurant

V. CONCLUSION

Mention here are the highest mean score from the data results gathered by the researchers and conclude the selected restaurants in Tagaytay City have no significant difference in terms of Human Resource, Natural resource, Technology, and Social and Political. Thus, the recommendation can be applied to everyone. For human resources, employees are trained properly especially in certain circumstances such as natural disasters. This will ensure that the staff have enough knowledge in handling natural disasters that can add to the safety of their customers. So that they can gain their trust and loyalty to the establishment and will feel secured during their entire stay. For the Natural resources, Al fresco or the outdoor seats were not usable because of dust and ashes. Due to it being outdoor dining, the tables and chairs were not usable and covered with ashes. This can also impact their sales for the day because the capacity of the establishment will not be able to accommodate the maximum numbers. For Capital Resources, the restaurant's wall was cracked due to earthquakes caused by the Taal eruption. This can also affect the guests coming to the establishment, we should ensure their safety and because of the cracks some restaurants will close to ensure that it will be fixed immediately because they are always after for the safety of the staff and customers. For Technology Resources, they used social media websites to advertise more about the restaurant. In promoting their restaurant, they used platforms such as Facebook and Instagram through sponsored posts that can help reach people easily. This can help generate more customers and respond to customers' queries and suggestions as soon as possible. For Social and Political factors, the restaurant advertises through social media by giving promotions. Following the restaurant's laws and regulations while promoting the establishment. This will help generate income and increase the establishment's reputation and help customers discover different Filipino Cuisines and Culture.

The researchers also concluded that there is at least one significant difference in terms of Capital Resources. This is due to the difference in scale of damage received of the establishments by the Taal eruption in Tagaytay City. The walls were cracked, and the establishments were damaged. Based on the gathered data, Restaurant A and B have a higher recovery strategy than the rest. It can be concluded that the selected restaurants recovered within a brief period with their recovery strategy. They can be a role model to other restaurants dealing with the same situations, help them know what areas they can improve, and gain more customers by ensuring customer's safety.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

Mention here are the lowest mean score from the data results gathered by the researchers and would like to recommend the following based on the recovery strategy of the selected restaurants in Tagaytay city:

The first recommendation is to optimize human resources in order to ensure that human capital is protected by employing and assigning extra work to employees in order to reduce the cost of hiring others to clean and renovate the establishment. Since they possessed the necessary training and talents to be a great employee, they should put them to good use and make the most of them in order to assist the restaurant in recovering from the natural disaster.

Since no vegetable garden has the lowest average of all natural resources, the second recommendation for the selected restaurant is green practices. Based on ipl.org, green practices in the foodservice industry are now more popular to consumers. Having their vegetable garden benefits their financial costs, it will save delivery expenses and cost of raw ingredients. This can ensure and attract customers by seeing how fresh their products serve. Since the selected restaurants have alfresco dining experience, this will freshen up the customers with the green environment and "instagramable" view of taal. It is Perfect for attracting "plantito's" and "plantita's" or people who love plants. The restaurants can also gain more extra income by selling green vegetables and other herbs.

The Third recommendation for the selected restaurants is to increase the menu prices for the time being. The result of increasing the menu prices in the survey has the lowest mean among all the questions in Capital resources, When the restaurant is being affected by the disaster, the supplies tend to be pricier because they are taking advantage of the disaster. Some businesses tend to increase prices to cope up with the losses caused by the disaster. This will help the restaurants lessen the losses while recovering from the damage taken. Then once the establishment has already recovered, they can put the price back to normal.

Based on the Technology result some of the restaurants must buy new appliances or repair their appliances because of the disaster so we decided that our fourth recommendation is to ensure that they Maintain their Appliances. Proper Maintenance of the appliances can help them reduce cost. Just like an establishment it needs proper cleaning to work

properly and to use it to the fullest. According to Handyman (2017) Bad habits cost you, good habits save thousands. When an establishment experiences a Natural Disaster, they should make sure that appliances such as Air-conditioning need to be cleaned right away.

Our last recommendation is to Prioritize the establishment's cleanliness in the aftermath of natural disasters so that customers will not be hesitant to visit the restaurant. You must demonstrate to guests that the restaurant is completely secure and presentable to them in order for them to feel more at ease dining in and enjoying the services and food that they offer.

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